

Reactions of Mercuric Acetate with Dialkyl Benzylphosphonates and Dialkyl Phenyl Phosphates

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Mercuric acetate gives with dialkyl benzylphosphonates (I), benzyl acetate and dialkyl acetoxymercuriphosphonates (II). In case of dialkyl phenylphosphates (IV), the alkyl acetates and alkyl phenyl acetoxymercuriphosphonates (VI) are obtained. The mechanism is discussed.

IN view of the broad physiological activity of organic phosphorus¹⁻⁵ and organic-mercury⁶ compounds, we plan to combine the organic-phosphorus and mercury compounds into one molecule.

The reaction of trivalent phosphorus compounds with mercuric carboxylates was reported by Teruaki, et al⁷. They have found that the mercurous and mercuric carboxylic acid salts were reduced by the trivalent phosphorus compounds, acetic anhydride was obtained along-with mercury and the corresponding pentavalent phosphorus compound.

To avoid the reduction process we focussed our attention⁸ on the pentavalent organic phosphorus compounds. In a 1:1 ratio, at room temperature, dialkyl benzylphosphonates (I) give with mercuric acetate benzyl acetate and dialkyl acetoxymercuriphosphonates (II). In the presence of excess mercuric acetate (two fold or more), at 100°, (I) gives a dimercurated phosphorus compound (III).

prepared by the method of Fox and Venezky⁹. The infrared spectra of (II) showed absorption bands at 1194 cm⁻¹ and at 936 cm⁻¹ due to P-O-Alk¹⁰. In the further mercurated compound (III) the intensity of the latter bands was decreased. The νP=O of compound (II) was found at 1300 cm⁻¹ which was shifted towards higher frequency, 1330 cm⁻¹ in compound (III).

The mass spectrum of the compounds (IIa and IIIa, R = C₂H₅), did not show the molecular ion peaks, M⁺, at m/e 398 and 670 respectively. The metastable ion peaks were also not detected. The base peak of (IIa) was found at m/e 43 due to the formation of the acetyl-onium ion, CH₃C≡O⁺. In compound (IIIa) the base peak was found at m/e 202, due to the mercurous ion Hg⁺. In compound (IIa), the Hg⁺ was observed but with a value m/e 95.5, with respect to the acetyl-onium ion.

As a result of elimination of (HgOAc) from the

The n.m.r. spectrum of (II) and (III) revealed signals of the alkyl protons, the aromatic protons were absent which confirms the decomposition of (I) by mercuric acetate. Dialkyl acetoxymercuriphosphonates (II) have been identified by comparison with an authentic

molecular ion of (IIa), the peak at m/e 137 may be interpreted as due to C₂H₅-O-P-O-C₂H₅. The intensity of this peak is relatively high (60 %), which may

indicate its relative stability. This ion showed a successive breakdown to give peaks at m/e 109 ($137-C_2H_4$)⁺, and at m/e 81 ($109-C_2H_4$)⁺. These fragmentations may be schematically summarised as follows :

Interestingly, in the mass spectrum of (IIIa), the fragment at m/e 137 as well as its degradation products at m/e 109 and 81 were not detected.

From the above data, we concluded that the reaction between mercuric acetate and dialkyl benzylphosphonates may proceed through an initial step, involving coordination of mercuric acetate with the phosphoryl oxygen. In the intermediate phosphonium ion, an intramolecular nucleophilic attack of the acetate group occurs on the benzyl moiety, and this type of phosphonium intermediate has been known to undergo rapid decomposition by cleavage of the C-P bond^{11,12}. The last step (a) can be considered as intramolecular Arbuzov rearrangement¹³.

A similar mechanism, as in the phosphonate (I) may be suggested, the corresponding intermediate phosphonium ion readily undergoes intramolecular nucleophilic attack of the acetate group on the alkoxy group, where

alkyl acetate and not phenyl acetate is obtained. This is confirmed by the fact that in aliphatic compounds containing the P⁺-O-C moiety have never been isolated¹⁴. Only when the carbon atom attached to oxygen is part of an aromatic ring, the phosphonium ion is stable¹⁴. Similarly, the second alkoxy group is removed as alkyl acetate to give (VI). The infrared spectra of (VI) showed absorption at 1190, 1240 cm⁻¹ due to ν P-O-C (aromatic), the absorptions at 986, 1052 cm⁻¹ due to ν P-O-C (aliphatic) completely disappeared.

It is interesting to report that even in the mercuriation of the phosphates (IV), although the phenyl group is not affected by mercuric acetate, P-O-C (aliphatic) fission occurred.

Experimental

Infrared spectra were measured on a Unicam SP200G spectrophotometer using Nujol technique. The nmr spectra were recorded on Varian A-60 in deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide using TMS as an internal reference. Mass spectra were determined with Hitachi spectrophotometer, using direct insertion technique, at a source temperature of 185° and electron beam energy 70 ev.

1. Preparation of dialkyl acetoxymcuryphosphonates (II) and alkyl phenyl acetoxymcuryphosphates (V).

When dialkyl phenyl phosphates (IV) was treated with mercuric acetate (1:1, at room temperature) it gave alkyl acetate and the mercurated organic phosphorus compound (V).⁴

When excess mercuric acetate (two fold or more) was allowed to react with (IV) at 100°, phenyl diacetoxymcuryphosphate (VI) was obtained.

A solution of 0.01 mole of the phosphonate (I) or the phosphate (IV) in 30 ml hexane was added to a suspension of 0.01 mole mercuric acetate in 20 ml hexane and the mixture was stirred at room temperature

for 6 hr. The precipitate was filtered and crystallised from toluene/petroleum ether (40-60°) for compounds (II) and from acetic acid for compounds (V). Compounds (II) were identified by comparison with an authentic prepared by the method of Fox and Venezky⁹. The physical and analytical data of compounds (V) are in Table 1.

TABLE 1

	R	X	Y	Molecular Formula	Found	% of Hg Calcd.
III a	C ₂ H ₅	HgOAc	HgOAc	C ₉ H ₁₁ Hg ₂ O ₇ P	63.71	63.96*
III b	n-C ₃ H ₇	HgOAc	HgOAc	C ₇ H ₁₃ Hg ₂ O ₇ P	62.30	62.57
III c	n-C ₄ H ₉	HgOAc	HgOAc	C ₈ H ₁₅ Hg ₂ O ₇ P	61.08	61.23
V a	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	OHgOAc	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ HgO ₆ P	43.15	43.55
V b	C ₆ H ₅	n-C ₃ H ₇	OHgOAc	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ HgO ₆ P	41.87	42.26
V c	C ₆ H ₅	n-C ₄ H ₉	OHgOAc	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ HgO ₆ P	40.90	41.05

- All the compounds are colorless, crystalline solid stable to 300°C.

* The composition was also checked by analysis for carbon and hydrogen, Found C, 11.74; H, 1.76; Calcd. C, 11.78, H, 1.8.

The acetate-esters were obtained from the filtrate after removing the solvents. They show the same physical constants and ir as authentic samples.

2. Preparation of alkyl diacetoxymercuryphosphate (III).

A solution of 0.01 mole of the phosphonate (I) in glacial acetic acid were added with stirring to a solution of 0.02 mole mercuric acetate in glacial acetic acid. The reaction mixture was heated on a water bath. A white crystalline solid separated out during heating. After about 6 hr, the reaction mixture was cooled. The precipitate formed was filtered off and crystallised from acetic acid. The yield of the products varied between 70-80%. The physical and analytical data of these compounds are in Table 1.

On working up the filtrate in the usual manner, the acetate-esters were obtained and identified by comparing the ir spectrum with an authentic sample.

3. Preparation of phenyl diacetoxymercuryphosphate (VI).

Dialkyl phenyl phosphate (0.01 mole) was dissolved in 30 ml glacial acetic acid. To this solution (0.02 mole) mercuric acetate in 20 ml acetic acid was added. The reaction mixture was heated on a water bath. A white crystalline solid separated out during heating. After about 12 hr, the reaction mixture was cooled. The precipitate was filtered off and crystallised from acetic acid. It decomposes above 300°.

Found Hg, 57.74, C₁₀H₁₁Hg₂O₈P requires Hg, 58.02,

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